

HUMAN RESOURCE PROGRAM IMPLEMENTATION, MOTIVATING STRATEGIES, AND EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE IN THE GOLDENHIGH-GARMENTS MANUFACTURING CORPORATION: BASIS FOR ENHANCED PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

The study assessed the HR program implementation of The Goldenhigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation and its relationship to the utilization of moderating strategies and employee performance to develop an enhanced program. Surveys were conducted to collect quantitative data from the employees, focusing on HR program implementation dimensions such as ability, motivation, and opportunity, as well as motivating strategies including intrinsic and extrinsic motivators. Additionally, the survey also focused on performance dimensions such as productivity and quality output. The data were statistically processed using weighted mean, Likert-scale, and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient to quantify the impact. This study used the quantitative descriptive-correlational method approach. The respondents were the employees of The Goldenhigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation. The findings revealed that the HR program implementation of the company in terms of ability, motivation, and opportunity was fully implemented with a general assessment of 3.81, 3.84, and 3.88 respectively. Moreover, there was no significant difference in the assessment of the heads and staff as to the level of HR program implementation with an obtained probability values of 0.860, 0.361, and 0.656. Additionally, the employees were highly performing in terms of productivity and output quality with a general assessment of 3.89 and 3.94 respectively, and the former determined that the amount of extrinsic motivators in the program was extremely motivating. Based on these findings, an enhanced program was proposed encompassing overall employee development strategies, skill-performance-centric program, capacity planning, and workflow management. The implementation of the enhanced program in the future was expected to optimize employee performance. Overall, this study provided valuable insights into enhancing the HR program with the ultimate goal of improving the employee performance of the company.

Keywords: *Human resource program implementation, Employee performance, Motivating strategies*

INTRODUCTION

Organizations not only focus on economic gain but also dwell on their internal corporate social responsibility toward their employees. As Akther et al. (2020) reiterated, employees were viewed as strategic resources that gave businesses a competitive edge. The majority of companies encountered people problems, which involved problems with productivity, efficiency, performance, and relationships of their employees. This was caused by poor implementation of Human Resource Management Programs. Effective implementation of these programs was substantially vital for any organization. Having poor programs impeded the fulfillment of the organization's objectives and goals. Moreover, it affected its overall financial position and competitive advantage.

As such, Djurovic (2020) stated that approximately 13,600 employees from 34 countries were surveyed and the results show that India tops the list with 89% satisfied employees. This high number of satisfied employees translated into the growing economy of India. India has transpired as one of the fastest-growing economies in the world and was anticipated to be part of the top economy after 10 years.

Additionally, India's GDP stood at US\$ 694.93 billion and was continuously increasing. Furthermore, according to McKinsey Global Institute, as cited by India Brand Equity Foundation (2021), the government of India increased its employment growth and created a more sustainable job setting to be highly competitive. While Lloyd and Thoman (2019) mentioned that it was a fact that an engaged workforce performing well and satisfied employees would lead to increased revenue for the company. These positive effects on the organization consequently benefited the economy of the whole country.

On the contrary, in the Philippines, there has been an increasing number of Filipinos leaving the country and looking for work abroad. According to the Philippine Statistics Authority (2020), as of 2019, there were an estimated 2.2 million OFWs, and this was increasing yearly. CNN (2020) reiterated that the main reason why Filipinos want to work abroad is because of better career opportunities. This was the reason why Philippine companies made sure to give importance to their employees. Azeez (2019) mentioned that good salaries and wages, proper benefits, job security, and career opportunities must be considered in its business operations. Satisfying the needs of the local workforce decreased the possibility of the workers leaving the country. Furthermore, Donthu (2022) mentioned that employees who were committed to the company and were happy with their jobs were unlikely to exhibit poor performance and were often very productive.

This study focused on a clothing manufacturing company located in the Province of Batangas. The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation has been in the industry for 45 years. It started its operations in 1977 as E&E Needlecrafts employing

approximately 1000 employees up to the year 2001. In 2004, it changed its name to Gee Line Garments International Corporation which employed approximately 600 employees. The decrease in the number of employees was attributed to the increasing number of competitors. Currently, the business changed its name to The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation due to the transition to second-generation family owners. Presently, the company has 101 employees. The drastic decline in the workforce was attributed to the decline in the garments manufacturing industry of the country.

In addition, the researcher is currently the Chief Operating Officer of the company. The management of the company was passed on to him from the first generation and it is his obligation to strengthen the position of the company in the industry. The former decided to focus the study on the company's human resource aspect as he finds it a vital factor for the success of the business. The remaining employees of the company were the loyal ones who had been in the company for more than 20 years. The business is labor-intensive, and this is the reason why the company must ensure the proper treatment of employees to stay competitive in the industry. The study looked into the company's Human Resource Programs and practices to see if they were effective in promoting job satisfaction and increased job performance. Increased job satisfaction and performance can lead to job loyalty and commitment. This loyalty and commitment can be the main factor that would slow down the decrease in the number of employees in the organization.

Moreover, the employees are valuable assets of any organization. They are the heart of the company. Without them, the company would not function. Therefore, efforts to improve human resource management programs should be made. When the management manages its employees properly, it will positively cultivate an individual's attitude, mindset, contentment, engagement, and commitment to the organization. Which in turn can increase productivity and organizational effectiveness. According to Inayat and Khan (2021), satisfied employees had higher effectiveness and efficiency compared to dissatisfied ones, consequently increasing the organization's competitive advantage. In today's fast-moving and highly competitive world, enhanced efficiency and effectiveness are keys to surviving and competing. This is where effective implementation of Human Resource Management Programs and practices comes in because these employee work engagements, value orientations, and associations greatly affect the productivity of any organization.

The review of the literature and studies that are pertinent to the suggested research study are presented in this chapter. Since the scope of the study centered on the satisfaction of The Goldenhigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation employees, the researcher pushed for the study promoting the Human Resource Programs of the company. However, the researcher searched and discovered that good studies have consistently been done on employee satisfaction and human resource programs by different individuals and institutions.

Implementation of Human Resource Programs

Several pertinent studies were developed to define and explain the significance of the effective and efficient implementation of Human Resource Programs in companies. The researchers initiated these studies since they saw a substantial link between Human Resource Programs and overall employee satisfaction. The impact of the programs on the employees was the decision criteria if the implementation was effective.

Correspondingly, Akther et al. (2020) reiterated that Human Resource Management literature was created as a result of the extensive research interest in the workplace and employees. Employees were perceived as strategic resources that gave businesses a competitive edge. The recent explosion in Human Resource Management study suggested that it had become a topic of interest to academics, researchers, and business professionals. One conference paper on people training in the field marked the beginning of the human resource management journey in 1981, but as of February 2020, a total of 1802 papers had been published and were indexed in the Scopus database.

In addition, Olasoji (2019) stated the concept of Human Resources Management developed as an independent concept in the middle of the 80s as a reasonable continuation of personnel management. Human resources were a vital aspect of progress, according to many authors. The ability to grow, move, and manage other elements was controlled by Human Resources Management. The difficulties in organizational performance in Human Resource Management emerged from a very varied range of businesses and industries. Due to the business environment's fast transformation, there were different issues in managing the human resources of any company. Numerous obstacles or changes were happening quickly that influenced Human Resource Management toward organizational efficiency in a wide-ranging variation of concerns due to the shifting economy as well as local and worldwide developments. Moreover, there were external factors that existed that hindered the overall efficiency and effectiveness of any company. Other issues that Human Resource Management faced were industrial and employee relations, workplace diversity, retention and succession plan, recruitment process, and accessibility of skilled workers and technology.

In the same way, Liu et al. (2020) claimed that the primary roles of Human Resource Management in an organization were to attract talents and meet their staffing needs to ensure smooth business flow. The HR function's sole responsibility in a traditional business is to maintain the workforce to satisfy output targets. This changed to one that is employee-focused as the business operations continue to evolve. Current businesses consider their employees as assets of the company. Consequently, Human Resource Management has focused on creating and sustaining an engaged, informed, progressive, and career-oriented workforce. Organizations in the modern era had realized how important staff development was to the overall success of the business. Employees were strategically developed into business assets through effective human resource programs. It concentrated on high-performance work structures that fostered employee competence, fidelity, and efficiency to provide a competitive edge. The

organization was better able to compete and flourish in the cutthroat business world by having devoted personnel.

Similarly, Al-Jedaiah and Albdareen (2020) mentioned that the foundation that defined how successful a company was was its human resources. The degree to which these resources were able to effectively exercise control over the various activities was determined by the depth and strength of the Human Resource Management. The needs of the business were identified through strategic planning for human resources, which also linked the HR strategy to the overarching organizational strategy. To achieve the company's aim in the markets, the strategy implemented identified the needs of the organization and advanced hand in hand with the organizational strategy. Additionally, the HR strategy outlined additional organizational requirements that aid in managing HR, such as the necessary experiences and training to enhance organizational skills. The success of the human resource strategy was beneficial to the overall organizational performance.

Additionally, Asis-Castro and Edralin (2020) emphasized that the most vital part of any company is its employees. They were essential in attaining the company's goals, vision, and mission. Human Resource Management needed to enforce Human Resource Programs that increased employee satisfaction and retention. These programs encapsulated recruitment, training, salary, reward, health and safety, and work-life balance. Moreover, the organization's Human Resource Programs displayed how much it values its people. Companies saw the intrinsic value of each employee and incorporated humanistic sustainability programs in dealing with them. By doing this, it guaranteed the welfare of every employee, and it created meaningful work for them. Additionally, this brought out a positive impact on the employees like happiness, trust, respect, recognition, emotional and mental stability, and overall well-being.

Furthermore, Fenech et al. (2019) reiterated that the performance of the organization was the primary concern of Human Resource Management. It was also emphasized that the purpose of Human Resource Programs was a solution for business problems concerning workforce effectiveness. Managing human resources was a strategic advantage for businesses that helped to increase the company's competitive edge. The senior management continued to view human resources as a drain on the business's budget until Human Resource Management reformed to administer the human resource department effectively. Human Resource Management in the digital era was more diversified and people-oriented, with the obligation of forming interesting, demanding positions to keep the young workforce involved in their work. The conventional methods that human resource responsibilities were handled in organizations were called into question by digital transformation. The digital revolution had further consequences for the purpose, capabilities, and competencies of Human Resource Programs. Therefore, digitization had an impact on Human Resource Management beyond simply making everyday administrative responsibilities simpler. The Human Resource Programs, which include planning, recruiting and selection, performance management, and incentive management, were made easier by the use of technology. However, these factors also increased the responsibilities placed on the human resource function, which

made sure that the organization's human capital was in connection with the strategic needs of the digital era.

Moreover, Bua and Margherita (2021) explained that Human Resource Management faces different challenges in the manufacturing industry. Nowadays, manufacturing organizations have adopted Industry 4.0 technologies – robots, the internet, and big data. This adaptation to change strategies was beneficial to the company since it increased production, lessened manufacturing costs, and created new products to be offered in the market. But these changes also had an impact on the workforce. With this technological adoption, the human workforce was being obliged to have a human-machine interaction. The function of Human Resource Management was to provide Human Resource Programs to establish an advantageous condition for employee development. The Human Resource Programs included practices that helped the workforce manage the new technologies. Moreover, these programs aimed to provide a higher level of technological knowledge, competencies, and capabilities, enjoyable working conditions, and greater self-development for increased job efficiency.

Therefore, Koster (2019) mentioned that innovative Human Resource Programs are very relevant in today's increasing global competition. This changing business environment entailed that the employees must continuously improve their skills, knowledge, and ability to perform effectively and efficiently. Innovative Human Resource Programs included equal treatment of employees, human capital investment, sustainable employability, incentive system, monetary incentives, decentralization, and autonomy. These programs contributed to organizational performance as they increased the performance, satisfaction, and loyalty of the workforce. Moreover, the programs adapted to different trends. These trends included social, technological, economic, political, environmental, and demographic trends. If human resource programs were conceptualized under these trends, then the employees would be directed toward the organizational goals. This strategy was well shown by 2003 research by Agarwala. 14 distinct Human Resource program domains were identified, including ones related to hiring processes, compensation schemes, and career growth. The basic theoretical tenet in this body of work was that, if Human Resources Policies and Programs were combined into bundles or systems, they improved business performance by raising employee engagement, performance, and commitment.

Specifically, Dvorakova (2020) deduced that sustainable Human Resource Management was the contemporary approach to managing employees. The Human Resource Practices and Programs not only focused on short-term employee development, restoration, and renewal. Having sustainable Human Resource Programs developed a maintainable working environment and in the long run, attained sustainable organizational goals. Moreover, to be sustainable, Human Resource Programs incorporated and correlated social and environmental concerns in their programs. This means that the management not only took into consideration their economic gain, but most importantly they promoted a balance between profit, environment, relationship with the community, and relationship with the whole company workforce. It was important that companies not negate the possible negative effects of their programs on the environment

and community. It was the moral obligation of organizations to operate ethically and to have a positive impact on all stakeholders.

In addition, Ramaraju (2019) noted that the foundation of Human Resource Programs was the definition of philosophical orientation, which aided in the focus of an organization's long-term, visionary concept. Management's outlooks and assumptions about people, which included their character, needs, worth, and work style, were at the central point of human resource philosophy. The treatment of individuals and the management's conception of its Human Resource Programs were thus determined by these ideas and presumptions. The programs were designed to handle individuals using one of three approaches: the humanistic approach, the machine approach, or the commodity approach. In the commodity approach, people were viewed as a good that could be bought or traded for a price, just like it was in the old slave practice. A human was regarded as an element or part of the machine that may be fitted like any other part of the machine. Both of these methods viewed persons as physiologically evident human beings. An individual was viewed as a human being with physiological characteristics in a humanistic approach.

Importantly, Ujma et al. (2019) cited that the foundations of the Ability, Motivation, and Opportunity (AMO) Theory were first found in Vroom's writings, where he asserted that both ability and motivation influenced performance. This method, however, ignored the impact of the outside world and concentrated entirely on individual traits. The opportunity factor, which reflected the working environment, equipment, supplies, leader behaviors, procedures, and time, was added by Blumberg and Pringle to this model. Individual performance, according to these writers, was a function of capacity (C, or abilities), willingness (W, or motivation), and opportunity (O). Suppose that $P = f(O \times C \times W)$, then performance (P) requires the presence of all three factors. A low level of any of these characteristics also had a significant negative impact on how well each individual performed.

Moreover, the Ability, Motivation, and Opportunity (AMO) theory has focused on assisting with the selection of Human Resource Programs that promote employee and organizational performance. Appropriate program selection was crucial for the deliberate modeling of employee abilities (i.e., selection, hiring, and training), motivations (i.e., performance-related pay), and opportunities to act (i.e., highlighting teamwork, or suggestion practices).

Furthermore, the three categories of Human Resource Programs were skill, motivation, and empowerment strengthening programs. The first goal of skill-enhancement programs was to raise knowledge, aptitude, and skill levels among employees so they could do their jobs effectively. Second, techniques that increased motivation were developed to guide employee behavior toward organizational goals by employing the right combination of inducements. Among these techniques were those related to performance management, pay, incentives, and rewards. Lastly, developing employee autonomy, participation in decision-making, raising employee accountability,

and providing feedback mechanisms were the main focuses of empowerment-enhancing techniques.

Motivating Strategies

People were primarily interested in motivation, or the ability to persuade oneself or others to do action. Managers face challenges in inspiring the employees, and employees themselves find it difficult to muster the willpower to persevere through life's and work's obligations. External factors like reward systems, grades, evaluations, or the opinions they think others may have of them frequently influence people. However, people were also often driven from within by innate passions, curiosities, deep-seated beliefs, or caring feelings. These internal drives fueled passions, creativity, and persistent work even when they were not always acknowledged or encouraged by others.

Hence, Salikhova (2020) cited that according to the Self-Determination Theory (SDT), both intrinsic and extrinsic motivators change and influence employees' performance. This theory proposed three basic psychological needs—autonomy, competence, and relatedness—as intrinsic motivators. Employees worked because they found them to be fascinating, entertaining, significant, or valuable. First, autonomy was the idea that one had free will and was voluntarily approving their action. Second, competence was the state of having mastered a task and being successful in it. Third, the urge to feel related to and a part of a group was referred to as relatedness. Furthermore, extrinsic motivators included the employee's social nature. Employees worked to get a reward or avoid punishment. It is also cited that numerous studies had demonstrated that both intrinsic motivators and the more self-determined types of extrinsic motivators contributed to both engagement and optimal job performance of the employees.

Supporting this, Rosli et al. (2022) asserted that the Self-Determination Theory led to the initial identification of the three fundamental needs of autonomy, competence, and relatedness based on their usefulness in integrating empirical research on the influence of interpersonal contexts and environmental occurrences on intrinsic motivation and the internalization of extrinsic motivation. These demands were critical for optimum motivation and general wellbeing, according to a later study. Vitality and need satisfaction were tightly associated, whereas motivational tiredness and need frustration were opposites. Depending on their performance, employees frequently responded to how much autonomy, competence, and relatedness they experience at work. More studies have shown that when basic needs aren't addressed, employees respond in predictable ways. Others made an effort to make up for what was lacking, as seen in their motivations for pursuing wealth, power, addictive diversions, or hostility as a result of need-frustrating. Others attempted to fill the void, as seen by their pursuit of riches, power, addictive vices, or anger as a result of need-frustrating.

Employee Performance

How well a person performed the tasks and obligations of their position was considered employee performance. For every organization, having vastly productive employees was important since they aided the organization reach its full potential. On the other hand, a business' success may be hindered and suffer if its employees perform poorly. Employee performance has generated significant attention and discussion in recent studies as a result of its expanding significance.

Due to this, Bashir et al. (2020) noted that an individual's degree of effectiveness in fulfilling their duties and capacity to achieve their goals served as an example of their overall job performance. The efficiency of the workforce was judged by how successfully a person carried out their responsibilities and other work-related tasks. The performance of a job was measured by the outcomes or effects of a certain work function or group of activities over a predetermined time frame. Since it was thought that these variables impacted organizational behavior or human resources practices rather than serving as a cause or determinant, employee performance was frequently the dependent variable in any empirical study.

To emphasize, Oyibo (2020) explained that employees were the company's most important asset and played a key role in performing organizational tasks and accomplishing organizational goals. How to maximize employee performance, though, was a dilemma for any organization. "The level of success of employees in performing their duties and responsibilities" was the definition of employee performance. Because employee performance was critical to evaluating whether organizational objectives were met, businesses searched for strategies to motivate their staff to perform at the top of their game.

Additionally, Inayat and Khan (2021) presented a research study that focused on the effect of job satisfaction on employees' job performance in different organizations in Peshawar, Pakistan. They concluded that satisfied employees had higher effectiveness and efficiency compared to dissatisfied ones, consequently increasing the organization's competitive advantage. Additionally, the study showed a positive relationship between work quality and job satisfaction. Most of the satisfied employees were relatively more competent, skillful, and committed at work. Because of the positive effect of employee satisfaction, the company gave the employees opportunities for personal advancement such as good salaries and wages, participation in decision-making, and increasing organizational participation. Moreover, the company focused on the employees' interpersonal relationships, workplace safety, incentives and rewards, and job security. Due to the economic and political stability in the region, it was the important role of the company to keep their employees motivated and satisfied in the current business setting.

Specifically, Ramos-Villagrasa et al. (2019) claimed that the most important factor in Human Resource Management was job performance. Its evaluation and analysis were crucial for many organizational procedures like hiring, paying, rewarding, or training

employees. Job performance was a paradigm that involved actions that employees may influence and that supported organizational goals. Task performance, contextual performance, and unproductive work behavior were the three essential areas of job performance. Together, these elements offered a comparatively systematic and economical process for evaluating total work performance. The first one was task performance, which was defined as "actions that influence the production of a good or service," followed by contextual performance, which was "actions that influence the goals of the company by aiding its social and psychological environment," and thirdly, counterproductive to work behavior, which was defined as "voluntary actions that harm the wellbeing of the company."

Moreover, according to Nuryanti et al. (2020), the crisis in employee performance was one of the most significant problems facing the management of any organization. The low intensity and unachievable work targets were caused by the subpar performance of human resources. Each worker performed in a way that accurately represented their role within the company. Employee creativity was limited, and as a result of subpar performance, work was completed in an inadequate amount and quality.

Supporting this claim, Aslan et al. (2021) reiterated that the conformity to carry out a duty within the terms of a contract between an employer and an employee was known as task performance. It was possible to define task performance as a person's capacity to efficiently do his or her tasks and obligations of the relevant function as outlined in the job description. In other words, it concerned how properly and successfully employees carried out their duties. Therefore, how well a person does his or her duties affects all aspects of the organization, including production, efficiency, and productivity. Task performance, in the eyes of the employee, was defined as behavior that was "expected, evaluated, and rewarded."

Correspondingly, Ertikin (2020) claimed that to thrive against changing environments, emerging technologies, and escalating competition, companies must be robust and adaptable. Employees were therefore immediately impacted by these processes that firms must deal with. To put it another way, maintaining standards was necessary for firms to prosper in the current competitive business climate. The best performance of employees within the standards was crucial to achieving high productivity in businesses. The term "performance" meant a notion that following a planned action was acquired and decided the outcome either statistically or qualitatively. Another definition of performance is that it is the specification of the quantity and quality of the planned goal that the individual or group conducting the activity can obtain.

With this in mind, Nugroho et al. (2021) explained that businesses and organizations need competent staff to advance. Employee output has revealed a person's capacity for work. When an employee had done high-caliber work that helped achieve every leader's task, this was referred to as performing well. The ability of an employee to complete their work by the deadline was another sign of their performance. Employee performance stems from the quality and quantity attained by an employee in carrying out his or her activities following the responsibilities assigned and it could reach

any aim set out by the firm. Each company had a high expectation of employee performance since the success of an organization cannot be divorced from the effectiveness of its workforce.

Moreover, Bienkowska and Tworek (2020) explained that the nature of today's jobs and the workplace are dynamic as a result of the changing and dynamic environment in which modern companies operate. Given that modern workers were the primary organizational resource defining the potential for sustainable development, it was necessary to reevaluate expectations for them. It was clear that employee intellectual capital enhanced organizational sustainability. Employees concentrated on making changes to be able to use their dynamic capacities to contribute to the organization's sustainable development. Therefore, contemporary firms viewed their workforce as a collection of fixed resources and developed the new competencies that were required for their effective performance of duties at a specific position. One of the essential elements required for attaining sustainable development in any modern business was the capacity of workers to adapt flexibly to changes in the environment, especially those that influence job performance. This combination of resources and flexibility was created as a result. To function effectively in today's dynamic and diverse world, "workers need to be increasingly adaptable, versatile, and tolerant of uncertainty."

In addition, Baskaran et al. (2020) stated that very little study had been done on how the use of technology in a company affected employee job performance and created job insecurity. Some researchers, however, discovered a connection between these features. Organizational policies and programs were altered as an effect of the adoption of new technologies. In the majority of organizations, the difficulties they encountered were brought on by modern technology, industry competitiveness, increased staff productivity, and new management and leadership. Numerous studies have demonstrated that improving staff attitudes and behaviors improves company performance.

Subsequently, Ong et al. (2020) explained that in many nations throughout the world, job satisfaction has been a well-sought topic. A person's degree of job satisfaction often determines how well they perform at work. A high degree of employee job satisfaction improved organizational performance. Researchers tended to be more motivated and eager to put in more effort when performing their jobs if they were happy with their present work. Employee attitude, loyalty, support, and devotion to the company may all be influenced by job satisfaction.

Correlation Studies between Human Resource Programs, Motivating Strategies, and Employee Performance

The function of effective implementation of Human Resource Programs was to positively cultivate and realize the potential of the employees – to increase their performance and consequently help aid the organization reach its goals. Therefore, it involved the formation of a people-centric Human Resource Program to improve employees' skills and quality and increase employee motivation and satisfaction.

To explain, Al-Tit (2020) showed that human resource programs had a favorable impact on the various facets of employee performance as a result of the creation of positive job satisfaction. This was supported by empirical evidence about the trilateral relationships between human resource programs, working environment, and job performance. The numerous facets of employee performance were tied to human resource programs. It specifically used the Ability, Motivation, and Opportunity framework. The idea that the use of human resource programs was meant to boost employee performance may be viewed as a composition of three elements, including programs that boost opportunities, motivation, and skill development. Analysts further argued, drawing on the social exchange concept, that when companies engage in various HR programs, which were likely to be seen by employees as a show of the company's commitment to them, employees responded in ways that supported business goals. Workers saw corporate initiatives like skill-, motivation-, and opportunity-enhancing programs as proof of the organization's commitment or support. Employees reciprocated by demonstrating a good attitude and improved performance that aided in the accomplishment of corporate objectives.

To expound, Tansel (2022) explained that while improved employee performance necessitated even more work, improved organizational performance indicated that attempts were being made to attain goals. Employee performance was one of the key factors that significantly influenced organizational success. Organizations have a significant impact on improving employee performance by offering efficient and effective human resource programs. In addition, management standards for assessing job performance were essential for improving employee performance since they demonstrated how actual performance relates to standards. The productivity of workers was impacted by both their internal and external work satisfaction. If the workforce were satisfied with both their occupations and their employer, they would be more strongly motivated to work hard to achieve the company's objectives.

Additionally, Tunio (2021) mentioned that people weighed their efforts to complete a job against the benefits related to the task assigned to them. They picked the tasks that satisfied the equation or those that offered more advantages or rewards. Therefore, the company's Human Resource Programs involved offering incentives following a person's expectations who was exerting a great deal of effort to complete a certain work. They were aware that their company appreciated the work they put in. Employees who were aware of potential connections between confident task outcomes would promote an individual's future attitudes and improve overall job performance.

Moreover, Donthu (2022) stated that many companies were struggling greatly in the current global environment to increase employee work satisfaction and, as a result, to strengthen their organizational commitment to obtain a competitive edge and maintain retention of their employees. The potential advantages for both people and organizations spurred a great deal of interest in organizational concepts that relate to attitude and behavior, such as organizational commitment, work satisfaction, and job performance. Employees who were committed to the company and were happy with their jobs were unlikely to exhibit poor performance and were often very productive. Companies

that achieved industry success were aware of how crucial employee retention was to maintaining market leadership and expanding their customer base. Employee satisfaction generally increased because they believed they were being compensated appropriately for the task they had completed. To achieve this, companies ensured that rewards given to employees were both true contributions to the business and consistent with the Human Resource Programs. Higher job satisfaction made employees more valuable because they felt that the company valued them in the long run and rewarded them for their hard work. As a result, they were more committed to the company, had greater retention rates, and were efficient with their overall job performance.

To support this, Andri et al. (2021) reiterated that any organization needs experienced, talented, and highly devoted staff for business operations to function smoothly. Due to competition, every business tries to retain as much of its workforce as possible. Employee performance determines whether an organization succeeds or fails since the employees are a company's most valuable asset. Therefore, a key component of human resource management was guaranteeing employee happiness and overall job satisfaction. When creating its programs, the management took into account elements like leadership, rewards, pay, skill development, career growth, and recognition. The inclusion of these elements in human resource programs led to longer-term employee retention and higher levels of employee satisfaction.

In addition, Thirusanku and Singh (2021) reiterated that organizational culture is the collection of common values, viewpoints, and beliefs that all employees share. The company's workplace culture was considered solid when the vast majority of its employees decided to adhere to the same principles. In conclusion, a robust and successful culture that aligned the company's aims with those of every individual worker would probably be able to attract workers who would collaborate to achieve organizational objectives.

However, Dumaguing (2022) restated the fact that a significant amount of research on employee performance has been done by academics from all around the world. Disengagement was discovered to be connected with characteristics that were both personal and professional. If workers felt they had adequate time for their personal lives, they were more likely to be satisfied with their occupations. They consequently developed greater motivation, engagement, and dedication to their work, which eventually increased output.

Importantly, Nor and Abdullah (2020) stated that the ability-enhancing practices, motivation-enhancing practices, and opportunity-enhancing practices (AMO) model of the human resource management of companies had been connected to the overall employee performance. The study showed that enhancing an employee's capacity, motivating them to produce high-quality work, and expanding their opportunities to interact with management produce favorable results for comprehending their preferences and helping them to reach the organizational goals in the workplace.

Synthesis

The literature reviews mentioned showed a great causal relationship between Human Resource Programs and employee job performance. As specified in the study of Akther et al. (2020) and Asis-Castro and Edralin (2020), employees are the strategic resources and assets of any organization. Without them, the organization would not function. They also mentioned that the employees were one of the factors that gave businesses a competitive advantage. Because of these claims, other scholars and business professionals have supported the belief that organizations must focus on the total human development of their employees as discussed by Liu et al. (2020), Al-Jedaiah and Albdareen (2020), Fenech et al. (2019), Bua and Margherita (2021), and Koster (2019).

Some studies about the importance of Human Resource Programs were pointed out by Andri et al. (2021). Moreover, Dvorakova (2020), Ramaraju (2019), Al-Tit (2020), Oyibo (2020), Ong et al. (2020), and Tansel (2022) revealed that Human Resource Programs were tools to motivate and help holistically develop employees. They also mentioned that motivated employees were more likely to be satisfied at work and contribute to their overall performance. To add to this, studies by Donthu (2022), Aslan et al. (2021), Ertikin (2020), Nuryanti et al. (2020), Dumaguing (2022), and Tunio (2021) stated that employees work and do the tasks that satisfied them or those that offered more advantages or rewards. Additionally, Bashir et al. (2020) noted that an individual's degree of effectiveness in fulfilling their duties served as an example of their job performance in the organization. To support this, Salikhova (2020) and Rosli et al. (2022) pointed out that numerous studies have demonstrated that both intrinsic motivators and the more self-determined types of extrinsic motivators contributed to both engagement and optimal job performance of the employees. In addition, Thirusanku and Singh (2021) reiterated that the company's organizational culture was considered solid when the vast majority of its employees decided to adhere to the same principles. However, there were also challenges that businesses faced with their human resources. Olasoji (2019), Bienkowska and Tworek (2020), and Baskaran et al. (2020) discussed that businesses need to be strong and flexible due to shifting circumstances, new technology, and intensifying competition. These procedures that businesses must cope with thus had an immediate effect on their employees. To put it another way, upholding standards was essential for businesses to thrive in the present business environment.

To conclude, according to Inayat and Khan (2021), Ramos-Villagrasa et al. (2019), Nor and Abdullah (2020), and Nugroho et al. (2021), there was a significant relationship between the level of implementation of Human Resource Programs and level of employee performance in businesses. Additionally, according to Ujma et al. (2019), appropriate program selection was crucial for the deliberate shaping of employee abilities. Ability, Motivation, and Opportunity (AMO) helped the selection of Human Resource Programs that promoted employee and organizational performance. It was challenging for any business to craft an effective and people-centric Human Resource Programs. However, for their business to grow and compete in the industry, the management must focus on the total human development of their employees through its Human Resource Programs.

The study on the “Implementation of the Human Resource Program, Utilization of the Motivating Strategies of The Goldenhigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation and Employees Performance” contributes to the literature by offering detailed insights, characterizing influential factors, posing practical recommendations, addressing gaps, and potentially progressing research methodologies. It adds depth to the understanding of employee performance in a specific context, informing the development of an enhanced human resource program. The study’s findings had rational implications for improving and expanding human resource programs and stimulating further research in this area.

The study effectively addressed key gaps in the existing literature on the implementation of human resource programs, utilization of motivating strategies, and employee performance. Through a thorough review of relevant research, the study made significant contributions by bridging the following gaps. Firstly, the study provided a comprehensive understanding of human resource program implementation by synthesizing diverse perspectives from the literature. It explored various factors affecting the proper implementation of human resource programs, including ability, motivation, and opportunity that the latter offered. By examining these factors, the study enhanced our knowledge of how to improve the human resource program of The Goldenhigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation.

Secondly, the study filled a gap in our understanding of the utilization of motivating strategies by reviewing and analyzing a range of studies. It identified the dimensions of extrinsic motivators and intrinsic motivators as vital contributors to motivating strategies. This exploration shed light on the specific factors that influence the company’s motivating strategies it has offered its employees.

Lastly, the study offered a thorough understanding of employee performance by synthesizing diverse perspectives from the literature. It explored key performance indicators that measured employee performance effectively, including productivity and output quality. This evaluation, sheds light on the specific indicators that influence employee performance, deepening our understanding of performance in this context.

In summary, the study’s comprehensive review of the literature and empirical research successfully filled important gaps in the understanding of human resource program implementation, motivating strategies utilization, and employee performance. By bridging these gaps, the study offers valuable insights into improving human resource program implementation and employee performance within The Goldenhigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation and similar businesses in the industry.

Research Questions

The primary goal of the study was to identify how the Human Resource Programs of The Goldenhigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation were implemented and how the employees responded through their job performance. To achieve a high level of employee performance, the company determined the important factors that were crucial in

effectively increasing job performance. This research specifically answered the following questions:

1. What is the implementation level of the human resource program of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation as assessed by its employees in terms of:

- 1.1 Ability,
- 1.2 Motivation, and
- 1.3 Opportunity?

2. Is there a significant difference between the assessment of the heads and employees as to the level of human resource program implementation of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation?

3. What is the performance level of the employees of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation in terms of:

- 3.1 Productivity, and
- 3.2 Output Quality?

4. What is the utilization level of the motivating strategies of the human resource program of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation in terms of:

- 4.1 Intrinsic Motivators, and
- 4.2 Extrinsic Motivators?

5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of implementation of the human resource program and the level of performance of the employees of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation?

6. Is there a significant relationship between the level of implementation of the human resource program and the level of utilization of the motivating strategies of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation?

7. Based on the findings of the study, what enhanced program may be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used a quantitative method with an emphasis on the descriptive-correlational method of research in defining the correlation between the implementation of Human Resource Programs of The Goldenhigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation as the independent variable and the level of employee performance as the dependent variable. The descriptive analysis was used as the study described, showed, and summarized the current level and standing of the variables. Moreover, correlational

analysis was also used as the study investigated and measured the causal relationships between the two variables using statistical data and tools.

According to Asenahabi (2019), the characteristic of the descriptive-correlational research method was to depict what was acquired in the data gathered via questionnaires and statistical treatment. It was likewise utilized to define profiles, frequency distribution, attributes of individuals, situations, experiences, and the causal relationships between variables.

Research Locale

The research was conducted at The Goldenhigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation in Barangay Poblacion, Padre Garcia, Batangas. Since the researcher works for The Goldenhigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation, the company was chosen as the locale of the study.

Population and Sampling

In this research, the stratified random sampling method was used in choosing the paralleling number of respondents. Nguyen et al. (2019) stated that the SRS, or stratified random sampling, was most effective when the population was divided into "strata" or smaller subgroups. A per-stratum sample was selected utilizing uniform random sampling from each stratum. The stratified random sample was made by conjoining all per-stratum samples. The population of The Goldenhigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation was divided into three groups – supervisors, quality controllers, and production operators. Therefore, the stratified random sampling was the most appropriate sampling technique to be used.

The sampling was established with a margin of error of 0.05, and a confidence level of 0.95, determined through the experienced knowledge of the researcher's statistician using the G*Power. Of the 101 population of The Goldenhigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation, a total of 96 (95% of their total employees) were chosen as respondents of this study.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were the employees of The Goldenhigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation for the fiscal year 2023.

Table A

Respondents of the Study

TYPE OF RESPONDENTS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Supervisor	5	5.21%

Production Operators	91	94.79%
Total	96	100.00%

The group of respondents consisted of five (5) supervisors, which was 5.21% of the total respondents, and seventy-three (91) production operators, which was 94.79% of the total respondents with a total of ninety-six (96) respondents.

Instrument

A researcher-made questionnaire was the instrument utilized in acquiring the primary data from each of the respondents. The questionnaire consisted of three (3) parts including multiple questions for each variable. The first section evaluated the implementation of the Human Resource Programs of The Goldenhigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation in terms of ability, motivation, and opportunity. The second evaluated the level of motivating strategies of The Goldenhigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation to their employees in terms of intrinsic motivators and extrinsic motivators. The third established the level of employee performance in terms of Productivity and Output Quality.

Mean-score Interval and Verbal Interpretation on the Level of Implementation of the Human Resource Program of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation

Ranges of Mean	Rating	Categorical Response	Verbal Interpretation
3.25 – 4.00	4	Very Satisfied	Fully Implemented
2.50 – 3.24	3	Satisfied	Implemented
1.75 – 2.49	2	Dissatisfied	Partially Implemented
1.00 – 1.74	1	Very Dissatisfied	Not Implemented

Mean-score Interval and Verbal Interpretation on the Level of Employee Performance of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation

Ranges of Mean	Rating	Categorical Response	Verbal Interpretation
3.25 – 4.00	4	Very Satisfied	Very Good
2.50 – 3.24	3	Satisfied	Good
1.75 – 2.49	2	Dissatisfied	Fair
1.00 – 1.74	1	Very Dissatisfied	Poor

Mean-score Interval and Verbal Interpretation on the Level of Motivating Strategies of the Human Resource Program of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation

Ranges of Mean	Rating	Categorical Response	Verbal Interpretation
3.25 – 4.00	4	Very Satisfied	Fully Utilized
2.50 – 3.24	3	Satisfied	Utilized
1.75 – 2.49	2	Dissatisfied	Partially Utilized
1.00 – 1.74	1	Very Dissatisfied	Not Utilized

To formulate precise answers and assess the quantitative value of the variable being assessed, a four-point Likert scale was utilized. The researcher's perspective and the following interpretation below were used to better clarify how the Likert scale was used in the study.

Validation of the Instrument

The instruments were initially tested on 10 employees not counted in the group of respondents. Validity was presumably the most crucial element in the design of any instrument used to assess research outcomes. Validating the instrument, the researcher consulted the instruments related to the study with the statistician for the researcher, Dean, Research Director, and professors of LCBA. They committed their time and efforts to take into account all the important problems that needed to be discussed and clarified during the research process. The computation determined that Lawshe's Content Validity Ratio attained the desirable standard of 1.0 based on percentage relevance. As a result, the scale's content validity has been well attained.

Furthermore, the reliability and consistency of the instrument's internal data were evaluated using Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient. The Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient indicates the extent to which items within scale or subscale are interrelated.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data gathering was conducted mainly on the survey questionnaire fulfilled and answered by the respondents. This survey questionnaire functioned as the research instrument and primary source of data for the study. To test the accuracy, validity, and reliability of the instrument used it is approved and validated by the Dean, Research Director, adviser, statistician, and professors. After the approval and validation of the instrument, the researcher mailed a letter directed to the Vice President of Human Resources requesting consent to collect data, through electronic mail, from the target respondents. Afterward, the data gathered from the instrument were then checked, tabulated, and submitted to the researcher's statistician. The former's assistance and guidance were utilized while the data were analyzed and interpreted to arrive at answers to the study's problem statement and hypothesis.

Scope and Delimitation

The scope of the study focused on evaluating the implementation of the human resource program of The Goldenhigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation in terms of ability, motivation, and opportunity. Moreover, it also examined the utilization of the motivating strategies the company provided its employees in terms of intrinsic motivators and extrinsic motivators. Additionally, it also assessed the performance level of the employees in terms of productivity and output quality.

The research design of the study was a descriptive correlational approach using a quantitative design. Furthermore, the data-gathering processes were restricted

essentially to the primary data that was collected from the respondents of the study and the related literature. There were limited studies evaluating the implementation of the human resource program of The Goldenhigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation. Hence, the resources of information were projected to be inadequate.

The respondents of the study were also limited to the heads and staff of The Goldenhigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation. The study was conducted during the 1st and 2nd semesters of the academic year 2023-2024.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: What is the implementation level of the human resource management program of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation as assessed by its employees?

1.1 Ability

Table 1.1

Level of Implementation of Human Resource Management Program of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing in terms of Ability

Indicators	Heads		Staff		Composite	
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI
The company programs						
1. promote workplace diversity and against workplace discrimination. (Ang mga programa ay nagtataguyod ng pagkakaiba-iba at laban sa diskriminasyon sa trabaho.)	3.80	FI	3.77	FI	3.79	FI
2. make sure that the job assignment is at the level of the abilities of the employees. (Tinitiyak ng mga programa na ang pagtatalaga ng trabaho ay nasa antas ng kakayahan ng mga empleyado.)	3.60	FI	3.80	FI	3.70	FI
3. respect the competence of each employee. (Iginagalang ng mga programa ang kakayahan ng bawat empleyado.)	4.00	FI	3.89	FI	3.95	FI
General Assessment	3.80	FI	3.82	FI	3.81	FI

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Fully Implemented (FI) 2.50-3.24 Implemented (I)
 1.75-2.49 Partially Implemented (PI) 1.00-1.74 Not Implemented (NI)

1.2 Motivation

Table 1.2

Level of Implementation of Human Resource Management Program of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing in terms of Motivation

Indicators	Heads		Staff		Composite	
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI
The company programs						
1. provide higher salaries compared to the industry average. (Ang mga programa ay nagbibigay ng mas mataas na suweldo kumpara sa ibang kumpanya.)	3.60	FI	3.77	FI	3.69	FI
2. provide better company-initiated benefits compared to other industry players. (Ang mga programa ay nagbibigay ng mas mahusay na mga benepisyo na pinasimulan ng kumpanya kumpara sa iba pang mga kumpanya.)	3.80	FI	3.79	FI	3.80	FI
3. give importance to the mental, emotional, and physical wellbeing of the employees. (Ang mga programa ay nagbibigay ng kahalagahan sa mental, emosyonal, at pisikal na kagalingan ng mga empleyado.)	3.80	FI	3.91	FI	3.86	FI
4. give rewards to employees who excels in their job performance. (Ang mga programa ay nagbibigay ng mga gantimpala sa mga empleyado na mahusay sa kanilang pagganap sa trabaho.)	3.80	FI	3.89	FI	3.85	FI
5. give punishment to employees with poor job performance. (Ang mga programa ay nagbibigay ng parusa sa mga empleyadong may mahinang pagganap sa trabaho.)	3.80	FI	3.90	FI	3.85	FI
6. include performance evaluation of employees. (Kasama sa mga programa ang pagsusuri sa pagtrabaho ng mga empleyado.)	4.00	FI	4.00	FI	4.00	FI
General Assessment	3.80	FI	3.88	FI	3.84	FI

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Fully Implemented (FI) 2.50-3.24 Implemented (I) 1.75-2.49 Partially Implemented (PI) 1.00-1.74 Not Implemented (NI)

1.3 Opportunity

Table 1.3

Level of Implementation of Human Resource Management Program of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing in terms of Opportunity

Indicators	Heads		Staff		Composite	
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI
The company programs						
1. provide the opportunity to improve the employee's skills and knowledge in the course of his or her work. (Ang mga programa ay nagbibigay ng pagkakataon na mapabuti ang mga kasanayan at	3.80	FI	3.91	FI	3.86	FI

kaalaman ng empleyado sa kurso ng kanyang trabaho.)						
2. provide an opportunity for the employee to advance his or her career. (Ang mga programa ay nagbibigay ng pagkakataon para sa empleyado na isulong ang kanyang karera.)	3.60	FI	3.85	FI	3.73	FI
3. give the employees to undergo training programs for their knowledge and skills advancement. (Ang mga programa ay nagbibigay sa mga empleyado na sumailalim sa mga programa sa pagsasanay para sa maisulong ang kanilang kaalaman at kasanayan.)	4.00	FI	4.00	FI	4.00	FI
4. promote autonomy to the employees. (Ang mga programa ay nagtataguyod ng awtonomiya sa mga empleyado.)	4.00	FI	3.89	FI	3.95	FI
5. promote teamwork and workplace camaraderie. (Ang mga programa ay nagtataguyod ng pagtutulungan at pakikipagkaibigan sa trabaho.)	4.00	FI	3.96	FI	3.98	FI
6. promote employee feedback and constructive criticisms. (Ang mga programa ay nagtataguyod ng feedback ng empleyado at magandang pagtanggap sa kritisismo.)	3.80	FI	3.97	FI	3.89	FI
7. provide an opportunity to increase knowledge through educational assistance. (Ang mga programa ay nagbibigay ng pagkakataon upang madagdagan ang kaalaman sa pamamagitan ng tulong na pang-edukasyon.)	3.80	FI	3.78	FI	3.79	FI
General Assessment	3.86	FI	3.91	FI	3.88	FI

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Fully Implemented (FI) 2.50-3.24 Implemented
 (I) 1.75-2.49 Partially Implemented (PI) 1.00-1.74 Not Implemented (NI)

Research Question 2: Is there a significant difference between the assessment of the heads and employees as to the level of human resource program implementation of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation?

Table 2
Test of Significant Difference Between the Assessment of the Heads and Staff as to the Level of Human Resource Program Implementation of The Golden High-Garments Manufacturing Corporation

Variables	T test	P value	Remarks	Decision
Ability	.177	.860	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Motivation	.919	.361	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Opportunity	.961	.656	Not Significant	Accept Ho

Research Question 3: What is the performance level of the employees of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation?

3.1 Productivity

Table 3.1

Performance Level of the Employees of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing in terms of Productivity

Indicators	Heads		Staff		Composite	
The employees	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
1. reach the hourly production output assigned to them. (Naabot ng mga empleyado ang oras-oras na produksyon na output na itinalaga sa kanila.)	4.00	VG	3.84	VG	3.92	VG
2. have a low absenteeism rate. (Ang mga empleyado ay may mababang antas ng pagliban.)	4.00	VG	3.82	VG	3.91	VG
3. reach the required cycle time to finish an operation of the of the production process. (Naabot ng mga empleyado ang kinakailangang bilis upang matapos ang isang operasyon ng proseso ng produksyon.)	4.00	VG	3.79	VG	3.90	VG
4. exceed the required hourly production assigned to them. (Nalalampasan ng mga empleyado ang oras-oras na produksyon na output na itinalaga sa kanila.)	4.00	VG	3.80	VG	3.90	VG
5. are required to have an overtime to finish the required output for the day. (Ang mga empleyado ay kinakailangang magkaroon ng overtime upang matapos ang output na itinalaga sa kanila.)	3.80	VG	3.80	VG	3.80	VG
General Assessment	3.96	VG	3.81	VG	3.89	VG

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Very Good (VG) 2.50-3.24 Good (G) 1.75-2.49 Fair (F) 1.00-1.74 Poor (P)

3.2 Output Quality

Table 3.2

Performance Level of the Employees of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing in terms of Output Quality

Indicators	Heads		Staff		Composite	
The employees	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
1. in-line inspection defect rate is within company standards. (Ang antas ng depekto ng in-line na inspeksyon ng mga empleyado ay nasa mga pamantayan ng kumpanya.)	4.00	VG	3.80	VG	3.90	VG
2. final inspection output defect rate is within company standards. (Ang antas ng depekto ng final na inspeksyon ng mga empleyado ay nasa mga pamantayan ng kumpanya.)	4.00	VG	3.93	VG	3.97	VG
3. Right First Time rate is within company standards. (Ang antas ng Right First Time ng mga	4.00	VG	3.89	VG	3.95	VG

empleado ay nasa loob ng pamantayan ng kumpanya.)

General Assessment	4.00	VG	3.87	VG	3.94	VG
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Legend: 3.25-4.00 Very Good (VG) 2.50-3.24 Good (G) 1.75-2.49 Fair (F) 1.00-1.74 Poor (P)

Research Question 4: What is the level of utilization of motivating strategies of the human resource program of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation?

4.1 Intrinsic Motivators

Table 4.1

Utilization Level of Motivating Strategies of the Human Resource Program of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing in terms of Intrinsic Motivators

Indicators	Heads		Staff		Composite	
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI
The employees						
1. are committed and loyal to the company. (Ang mga empleyado ay nakatuon at tapat sa kumpanya.)	4.00	FU	3.86	FU	3.93	FU
2. feel accountable with the job they do. (Pakiramdam ng mga empleyado ay may pananagutan sila sa trabahong kanilang ginagawa.)	4.00	FU	3.88	FU	3.94	FU
3. enjoy doing the job assigned to them. (Ang mga empleyado ay nasisiyahan sa paggawa ng trabahong itinalaga sa kanila.)	3.80	FU	3.81	FU	3.81	FU
4. are not burnout with their responsibilities. (Ang mga empleyado ay hindi burnout sa kanilang mga responsibilidad.)	3.80	FU	3.81	FU	3.81	FU
5. do not feel stagnant in the company. (Ang mga empleyado ay hindi nakakaramdam ng walang pag-unlad sa kumpanya.)	3.80	FU	3.80	FU	3.80	FU
General Assessment	3.88	FU	3.83	FU	3.86	FU

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Fully Utilized (FU) 2.50-3.24 Utilized (U)
1.75-2.49 Moderately Utilized (MU) 1.00-1.74 Not Utilized (NU)

4.2 Extrinsic Motivators

Table 4.2

Utilization Level of Motivating Strategies of the Human Resource Program of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing in terms of Extrinsic Motivators

Indicators	Heads		Staff		Composite	
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI
The employees						
1. seek further knowledge and skills to go up the corporate ladder. (Ang mga empleyado ay naghahanap ng karagdagang kaalaman at kasanayan upang mapataas ang posisyon sa kumpanya.)	3.80	FU	3.89	FU	3.85	FU

2. seek to receive rewards for their job to keep them motivated to work. (Ang mga empleyado ay naghahangad na makatanggap ng mga gantimpala upang mapanatili silang masigla magtrabaho.)	4.00	FU	3.98	FU	3.99	FU
3. receive punishment for their poor job performance to let them push themselves to be better. (Ang mga empleyado ay tumatanggap ng parusa para sa kanilang mahinang pagganap sa trabaho upang itulak nila ang kanilang sarili na maging mas mahusay.)	4.00	FU	3.94	FU	3.97	FU
General Assessment	3.93	FU	3.93	FU	3.93	FU

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Fully Utilized (FU) 2.50-3.24 Utilized (U)
1.75-2.49 Moderately Utilized (MU) 1.00-1.74 Not Utilized (NU)

Research Question 5: Is there a significant relationship between the level of implementation of the human resource program and the level of performance of the employees of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation?

Table 5
Test of Significant Relationship between the Level of Implementation of Human Resource Program and the Level of Performance of the Employees of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation

Sales performance	Job Satisfaction of self-employed	r value	p value	Remarks	Decision
Ability	Productivity	.004	.970	Not Significant	Accept ho
	Output Quality	.190	.064	Not Significant	Accept ho
Motivation	Productivity	.173	.091	Not Significant	Accept ho
	Output Quality	.052	.616	Not Significant	Accept ho
Opportunity	Productivity	.040	.698	Not Significant	Accept ho
	Output Quality	.172	.094	Not Significant	Accept ho

Research Question 6: Is there a significant relationship between the level of implementation of the human resource program and the utilization level of the motivating strategies of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation?

Table 6
Test of Significant Relationship between the Level of Implementation of Human Resource Program and Utilization Level of the Motivating Strategies of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation

Human resource program	Motivating Strategies	r value	p value	Remarks	Decision
		.147	.152		
		686			

Ability	Intrinsic			Not Significant	Accept ho
	Extrinsic	.187	.068	Not Significant	Accept ho
Motivation	Intrinsic	.111	.281	Not Significant	Accept ho
	Extrinsic	.302**	.003	Significant	Reject ho
Opportunity	Intrinsic	.398**	.000	Significant	Reject ho
	Extrinsic	.284**	.005	Significant	Reject ho

Research Question 7: Based on the findings of the study, what enhanced program may be proposed?

Table 7
The Proposed Enhanced Plan

KEY AREAS	OBJECTIVES	STRATEGIES/ ACTIVITIES	TIME FRAME	PERSONS INVOLVED	SUCCESS INDICATRS
Implementation of human resource program in terms of Ability	Enhance ability aspect of the human resource program	Job-Skills matching of employees	Ongoing	Human Resource Department	Increased employee application rate
Implementation of human resource program in terms of Motivation	Enhance the motivation aspect of the human resource program	Offering performance based rewards	Ongoing	Human Resource Department	Increased scores in performance evaluation
Implementation of human resource program in terms of Opportunity	Enhance the opportunity aspect of the human resource program	Performance based promotion program	Ongoing	Human Resource Department	Increased employee retention rate
Motivating strategies in terms of Intrinsic Motivators	Enhance the intrinsic motivator aspect of the motivating strategies	Offering non-monetary benefits	Ongoing	Human Resource Department	Increased employee satisfaction feedback
Motivating strategies in terms of Extrinsic Motivators	Enhance the extrinsic motivator aspect of the motivating strategies	“Choose your own” rewards program	Ongoing	Human Resource Department	Increased employee satisfaction feedback
Employee performance in terms of Productivity	Improve employee productivity	Hire an Industrial Engineer to streamline workflow processes	3 Months	Heads, Operations Department	Increased production output and Decreased overtime

Employee performance in terms of Output Quality	Improve employee output quality	Quality assurance training and development	Ongoing	Heads, Quality Controllers	Decreased defect rate
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DISCUSSION

Research Question 1: What is the implementation level of the human resource management program of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation as assessed by its employees?

1.1 Ability

Table 1.1

Level of Implementation of Human Resource Management Program of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing in terms of Ability

Indicators	Heads		Staff		Composite	
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI
The company programs						
1. promote workplace diversity and against workplace discrimination. (Ang mga programa ay nagtataguyod ng pagkakaiba-iba at laban sa diskriminasyon sa trabaho.)	3.80	FI	3.77	FI	3.79	FI
2. make sure that the job assignment is at the level of the abilities of the employees. (Tinitiyak ng mga programa na ang pagtatalaga ng trabaho ay nasa antas ng kakayahan ng mga empleyado.)	3.60	FI	3.80	FI	3.70	FI
3. respect the competence of each employee. (Iginagalang ng mga programa ang kakayahan ng bawat empleyado.)	4.00	FI	3.89	FI	3.95	FI
General Assessment	3.80	FI	3.82	FI	3.81	FI

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Fully Implemented (FI) 2.50-3.24 Implemented (I)
1.75-2.49 Partially Implemented (PI) 1.00-1.74 Not Implemented (NI)

Ability was Fully Implemented (3.81) as to the level of the implementation of the human resource program of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation. “The company programs respect the competence of each employee” had the highest mean which was **3.95** and was interpreted as **Fully Implemented**. On the other hand, “The company programs make sure that the job assignment is at the level of the abilities of the employees” received the lowest mean score of responses with 3.70 and was interpreted as **Fully Implemented**.

This implies that the GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation employees were very satisfied with the company’s human resource program in terms of Ability. The company’s policies were specific, relevant, and well-known by the employees, and played a major role in ensuring the employees were mindful of their capabilities and skills in helping achieve operational goals and objectives. The GoldenHigh-Garments

Manufacturing Corporation is continually developing tactics to make sure that the employees are well-informed about the skills, knowledge, and abilities needed to perform their jobs efficiently. By doing this, the employees are a step in attaining a good job performance to help the company achieve operational efficiency.

To support the study, Importantly, Nor and Abdullah (2020) cited that the ability-enhancing practices of the human resource management of companies had been connected to overall employee performance. The study showed that enhancing an employee's capacity produces favorable results for comprehending their preferences and helping them to reach the organizational goals in the workplace.

Furthermore, Ujma et al. (2019) asserted that the ability of employees influenced performance. The first goal of skill-enhancement programs was to raise knowledge, aptitude, and skill levels among employees so they could do their jobs effectively. If the skills of the employees were monitored and enhanced, then the company would benefit. The former helped the latter by reaching organizational effectiveness and by helping compete in the industry.

1.2 Motivation

Table 1.2

Level of Implementation of Human Resource Management Program of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing in terms of Motivation

Indicators	Heads		Staff		Composite	
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI
The company programs						
1. provide higher salaries compared to the industry average. (Ang mga programa ay nagbibigay ng mas mataas na suweldo kumpara sa ibang kumpanya.)	3.60	FI	3.77	FI	3.69	FI
2. provide better company-initiated benefits compared to other industry players. (Ang mga programa ay nagbibigay ng mas mahusay na mga benepisyo na pinasimulan ng kumpanya kumpara sa iba pang mga kumpanya.)	3.80	FI	3.79	FI	3.80	FI
3. give importance to the mental, emotional, and physical wellbeing of the employees. (Ang mga programa ay nagbibigay ng kahalagahan sa mental, emosyonal, at pisikal na kagalingan ng mga empleyado.)	3.80	FI	3.91	FI	3.86	FI
4. give rewards to employees who excels in their job performance. (Ang mga programa ay nagbibigay ng mga gantimpala sa mga empleyado na mahusay sa kanilang pagganap sa trabaho.)	3.80	FI	3.89	FI	3.85	FI
5. give punishment to employees with poor job performance. (Ang mga programa ay nagbibigay ng parusa sa mga empleyadong may mahinang pagganap sa trabaho.)	3.80	FI	3.90	FI	3.85	FI

6. include performance evaluation of employees.
(Kasama sa mga programa ang pagsusuri sa pagtrabaho ng mga empleyado.)

	4.00	FI	4.00	FI	4.00	FI
General Assessment	3.80	FI	3.88	FI	3.84	FI
Legend:	3.25-4.00 Fully Implemented (FI)		2.50-3.24 Implemented (I)			
	1.75-2.49 Partially Implemented (PI)		1.00-1.74 Not Implemented (NI)			

Motivation was Fully Implemented (3.84) as to the level of implementation of the human resource program of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation. The indicator “The company programs include performance evaluation of employees” had the highest mean which was **4.00** and was interpreted as **Fully Implemented**. On the contrary, “The company programs provide higher salaries compared to the industry average” had the lowest mean which was **3.69**, and was interpreted as **Fully Implemented**.

This indicates that the employees observed the motivation aspect of the human resource program of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation because the former identified it as a vital indicator of a company’s work towards ensuring the efficient work of employees. Companies are paying close attention to employee engagement these days and with good reason—high levels of employee engagement are inextricably related to high levels of employee motivation. The human resource program of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation makes sure that their employees are motivated by doing performance evaluations regularly, following legal compensation-benefits programs, providing competitive compensation-benefits programs, focusing on the mental well-being of the employees, and giving rewards and punishment for job performance. With the findings, the indicators showed that the human resource program of the company motivates its employees. The indicator that yielded the highest mean – “The company programs include performance evaluation of employees”, serves as the company’s essential communication tool. It helped the employees align with the objectives set for the company and close the gap between expected and actual results. Employee performance reviews have provided insightful criticism for areas where performance is deficient, track development, and acknowledge good work.

To support this, Inayat and Khan (2021) conducted a research study that focused on the effect of job satisfaction on employees’ job performance in different organizations. They concluded that motivated employees had higher effectiveness and efficiency compared to unmotivated ones, consequently increasing the organization’s competitive advantage. Additionally, the study showed a positive correlation between work quality and job satisfaction. Most of the satisfied employees were relatively more competent, skillful, and committed at work. Moreover, they reiterated that companies focused on programs that motivated the employees. The former focused on the employees’ compensation, incentives and rewards, and job security.

Furthermore, Asis-Castro and Edralin (2020) emphasized that the most vital part of any company was its employees. They were vital in attaining the company’s goals and objectives. The human resource program of any company was needed to increase employee satisfaction. These programs encompassed recruitment, training, salary,

reward, health and safety, and work-life balance. In addition, companies saw the intrinsic value of each employee and included humanistic sustainability programs in dealing with them. By doing this, it guaranteed the welfare of every employee, and it created meaningful work for them. Additionally, this brought out a positive impact on the employees like happiness, trust, respect, recognition, emotional and mental stability, and overall well-being. This proved that the human resource program of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation in the aspect of motivation ensured that the employees maintain a high level of satisfaction. Consequently, this level of motivation and satisfaction resulted in higher efficiency and productivity of the employees.

1.3 Opportunity

Table 1.3

Level of Implementation of Human Resource Management Program of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing in terms of Opportunity

Indicators	Heads		Staff		Composite	
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI
The company programs						
1. provide the opportunity to improve the employee's skills and knowledge in the course of his or her work. (Ang mga programa ay nagbibigay ng pagkakataon na mapabuti ang mga kasanayan at kaalaman ng empleyado sa kurso ng kanyang trabaho.)	3.80	FI	3.91	FI	3.86	FI
2. provide an opportunity for the employee to advance his or her career. (Ang mga programa ay nagbibigay ng pagkakataon para sa empleyado na isulong ang kanyang karera.)	3.60	FI	3.85	FI	3.73	FI
3. give the employees to undergo training programs for their knowledge and skills advancement. (Ang mga programa ay nagbibigay sa mga empleyado na sumailalim sa mga programa sa pagsasanay para sa maisulong ang kanilang kaalaman at kasanayan.)	4.00	FI	4.00	FI	4.00	FI
4. promote autonomy to the employees. (Ang mga programa ay nagtataguyod ng awtonomiya sa mga empleyado.)	4.00	FI	3.89	FI	3.95	FI
5. promote teamwork and workplace camaraderie. (Ang mga programa ay nagtataguyod ng pagtutulungan at pakikipagkaibigan sa trabaho.)	4.00	FI	3.96	FI	3.98	FI
6. promote employee feedback and constructive criticisms. (Ang mga programa ay nagtataguyod ng feedback ng empleyado at magandang pagtanggap sa kritisismo.)	3.80	FI	3.97	FI	3.89	FI
7. provide an opportunity to increase knowledge through educational assistance. (Ang mga programa ay nagbibigay ng pagkakataon upang madagdagan ang kaalaman sa pamamagitan ng tulong na pang- edukasyon.)	3.80	FI	3.78	FI	3.79	FI
General Assessment	3.86	FI	3.91	FI	3.88	FI

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Fully Implemented (FI) 2.50-3.24 Implemented (I)
1.75-2.49 Partially Implemented (PI) 1.00-1.74 Not Implemented (NI)

Opportunity was **Fully Implemented (3.88)** as to the level of implementation of the human resource program of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation. The indicator “The company programs give the employees to undergo training programs for their knowledge and skills advancement” had the highest mean which was **4.00** verbally interpreted as **Fully Implemented**. Meanwhile, the indicator “The company programs provide an opportunity for the employee to advance his or her career” had the lowest mean which was **3.73** verbally interpreted as **Fully Implemented**.

This reveals that The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation employees were very satisfied with the company’s human resource program in terms of opportunity because the indicators showed that the employees felt personal and career growth in the company. Since the human resource program of the company focused on knowledge and skills training and development, the employees felt an opportunity to advance their careers.

To support this claim, Koster (2019) mentioned that innovative human resource programs were very relevant in today’s increasing global competition. This changing business environment entailed that the employees must continuously improve their skills, knowledge, and ability to perform effectively and efficiently. These programs contributed to organizational performance as they increased the performance, satisfaction, and loyalty of the workforce.

Moreover, Bua and Margherita (2021) stated that the function of Human Resource Management was to provide human resource programs to establish an advantageous condition for employee development. These programs included practices that helped the workforce manage new technologies. Additionally, these programs aimed to provide a higher level of technological knowledge, competencies, and capabilities, enjoyable working conditions, and greater self-development for increased job efficiency and performance.

Research Question 2: Is there a significant difference between the assessment of the heads and employees as to the level of human resource program implementation of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation?

Table 2

Test of Significant Difference Between the Assessment of the Heads and Staff as to the Level of Human Resource Program Implementation of The Golden High-Garments Manufacturing Corporation

Variables	T test	P value	Remarks	Decision
Ability	.177	.860	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Motivation	.919	.361	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Opportunity	.961	.656	Not Significant	Accept Ho

There was no significant difference in the assessment of the heads and staff as to the level of human resource program implementation of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation. The probability values of 0.860, 0.361, and 0.656 respectively were greater than the level of significance at 0.05, thus rejecting the null hypothesis.

The findings in the assessment of the heads and employees can be attributed to the fact that the heads and employees both have the same point of view of the human resource program implementation of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation. Both the heads and employees benefit equally from the implementation of the human resource program of the company.

Moreover, the heads and employees of the company share the same values and beliefs thus having an effective organizational culture. Having the same beliefs and values could also be the reason why there was no significant difference between the assessment of the heads and staff as to the level of human resource program implementation of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation.

To support this claim, Thirusanku and Singh (2021) reiterated that organizational culture was the set of shared values, opinions, and beliefs held by all members of the workforce. When the majority of employees chose to uphold the same values within the company, that workplace culture was said to be strong. In summary, a strong and effective culture that matched the objectives of the company with those of each employee was likely to be able to draw in employees who would work hand in hand in attaining organizational goals.

Research Question 3: What is the performance level of the employees of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation?

3.1 Productivity

Productivity was Very Good (3.89) as to the performance level of the employees of the Goldenhigh-Garments Manufacturing. The indicator “The employees reach the hourly production output assigned to them” had the highest mean of **3.92** verbally interpreted as **Very Good** while the indicator “The employees are required to have overtime to finish the required output of the day” had the lowest mean of **3.80** verbally interpreted as **Very Good**.

Table 3.1

Performance Level of the Employees of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing in terms of Productivity

Indicators	Heads		Staff		Composite	
	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
The employees	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
1. reach the hourly production output assigned to them. (Naabot ng mga empleyado ang oras-oras na produksyon na output na itinalaga sa kanila.)	4.00	VG	3.84	VG	3.92	VG
2. have a low absenteeism rate. (Ang mga empleyado ay may mababang antas ng pagliban.)	4.00	VG	3.82	VG	3.91	VG
3. reach the required cycle time to finish an operation of the of the production process. (Naabot ng mga empleyado ang kinakailangang bilis upang matapos ang isang operasyon ng proseso ng produksyon.)	4.00	VG	3.79	VG	3.90	VG
4. exceed the required hourly production assigned to them. (Nalalampasan ng mga empleyado ang oras-oras na produksyon na output na itinalaga sa kanila.)	4.00	VG	3.80	VG	3.90	VG
5. are required to have an overtime to finish the required output for the day. (Ang mga empleyado ay kinakailangang magkaroon ng overtime upang matapos ang output na itinalaga sa kanila.)	3.80	VG	3.80	VG	3.80	VG
General Assessment	3.96	VG	3.81	VG	3.89	VG

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Very Good (VG) 2.50-3.24 Good (G) 1.75-2.49 Fair (F) 1.00-1.74 Poor (P)

This implies that the employees of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation are always performing highly in terms of productivity. The employees generally reach the hourly production output assigned to them, reach the required cycle time to finish an operation of the production process, exceed the required hourly production assigned to them, and have a low absenteeism rate. These indicate that the employees of the company are generally efficient and productive in doing the job assignments.

Nugroho et al. (2021) explained that employee output revealed a person's capacity for work. When an employee had done exceptional work that was useful in accomplishing every leader's task, this was referred to as performing well. The capacity of an employee to accomplish their work by the deadline was another measure of their performance. As noted, employee performance arose from the quality and quantity reached by an employee in performing his or her duties in line with the duties assigned and it can reach any target set out by the company. Every business had high standards of employee performance because the success of a business cannot be detached from the efficiency of its employees.

3.2 Output Quality

Table 3.2

Performance Level of the Employees of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing in terms of Output Quality

Indicators	Heads		Staff		Composite	
	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
The employees	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
1. in-line inspection defect rate is within company standards. (Ang antas ng depekto ng in-line na inspeksyon ng mga empleyado ay nasa mga pamantayan ng kumpanya.)	4.00	VG	3.80	VG	3.90	VG
2. final inspection output defect rate is within company standards. (Ang antas ng depekto ng final na inspeksyon ng mga empleyado ay nasa mga pamantayan ng kumpanya.)	4.00	VG	3.93	VG	3.97	VG
3. Right First Time rate is within company standards. (Ang antas ng Right First Time ng mga empleyado ay nasa loob ng pamantayan ng kumpanya.)	4.00	VG	3.89	VG	3.95	VG
General Assessment	4.00	VG	3.87	VG	3.94	VG

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Very Good (VG) 2.50-3.24 Good (G) 1.75-2.49 Fair (F) 1.00-1.74 Poor (P)

Output Quality was Very Good (3.97) as to the performance level of the employees of the Goldenhigh-Garments Manufacturing. The indicator “The employees’ final inspection output defect rate is within company standards and buyer inspection output defect rate is within standards” had the highest mean of **3.97** verbally interpreted as **Very Good** while the indicator “The employees’ in-line inspection defect rate is within company standards” had the lowest mean with **3.90** verbally interpreted as **Very Good**.

The tables indicate that the employees of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation are always performing highly in terms of quality output. The employees’ in-line inspection rate, final inspection output defect rate, buyer inspection output defect rate, Right First Time rate, and overall quality output rate are within standards. This indicates that the work output of employees of the company is of high quality. This means that the job performance of the employees of the company is of high standard since the output of their work is of high quality.

To support this claim, Nuryanti et al. (2020) explained that one of the most important issues faced by any company's management was the crisis in employee performance. The poor performance of human resources was the cause of the low intensity and inaccessibility of work targets. Every employee's performance was a genuine behavior that reflected their function inside the organization. Employee inventiveness was low and work was done in an unsatisfactory quantity and quality as a result of poor performance.

Research Question 4: What is the level of utilization of motivating strategies of the human resource program of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation?

4.1 Intrinsic Motivators

Intrinsic Motivators was **Fully Utilized (3.86)** as to the utilization level of motivating strategies of the human resource program of the GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing. The indicator “The employees feel accountable with the job they do” had the highest mean of **3.94** verbally interpreted as **Fully Utilized** while the indicator “The employees do not feel stagnant in the company” had the lowest mean of **3.80** verbally interpreted as **Fully Utilized**.

Table 4.1
Utilization Level of Motivating Strategies of the Human Resource Program of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing in terms of Intrinsic Motivators

Indicators	Heads		Staff		Composite	
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI
The employees						
1. are committed and loyal to the company. (Ang mga empleyado ay nakatuon at tapat sa kumpanya.)	4.00	FU	3.86	FU	3.93	FU
2. feel accountable with the job they do. (Pakiramdam ng mga empleyado ay may pananagutan sila sa trabahong kanilang ginagawa.)	4.00	FU	3.88	FU	3.94	FU
3. enjoy doing the job assigned to them. (Ang mga empleyado ay nasisiyahan sa paggawa ng trabahong itinalaga sa kanila.)	3.80	FU	3.81	FU	3.81	FU
4. are not burnout with their responsibilities. (Ang mga empleyado ay hindi burnout sa kanilang mga responsibilidad.)	3.80	FU	3.81	FU	3.81	FU
5. do not feel stagnant in the company. (Ang mga empleyado ay hindi nakakaramdam ng walang pag-unlad sa kumpanya.)	3.80	FU	3.80	FU	3.80	FU
General Assessment	3.88	FU	3.83	FU	3.86	FU

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Fully Utilized (FU) 2.50-3.24 Utilized (U)
1.75-2.49 Moderately Utilized (MU) 1.00-1.74 Not Utilized (NU)

This implies that using intrinsic motivators as a motivating strategy is effective in crafting the human resource program of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation. This type of motivator enables the employees to perform a task for its own sake if it aligns with their interests, passions, and personal values. This would lead to higher job performance and increased dedication and loyalty to the company.

To support this, Salikhova (2020) cited that according to the Self-Determination Theory, intrinsic motivators influence employees' performance. This theory proposed three basic psychological needs—autonomy, competence, and relatedness—as intrinsic motivators. Employees work because they find them to be fascinating, entertaining, significant, or valuable. Employees who felt valuable in the workplace stayed

in the company longer. They were effective in helping reach organizational goals and objectives. Employees have gone above and beyond to ensure that their job is of the highest caliber when they genuinely believe in it. They took the initiative on new prospects and finished them by the deadline since they were more focused and detail-oriented. Moreover, an employee felt more comfortable and motivated if their employer supported their values and goals. This resulted in an increased level of dedication from the employees towards the company.

4.2 Extrinsic Motivators

Table 4.2

Utilization Level of Motivating Strategies of the Human Resource Program of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing in terms of Extrinsic Motivators

Indicators	Heads		Staff		Composite	
	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
The employees	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
1. seek further knowledge and skills to go up the corporate ladder. (Ang mga empleyado ay naghahanap ng karagdagang kaalaman at kasanayan upang mapataas ang posisyon sa kumpanya.)	3.80	FU	3.89	FU	3.85	FU
2. seek to receive rewards for their job to keep them motivated to work. (Ang mga empleyado ay naghahangad na makatanggap ng mga gantimpala upang mapanatili silang masigla magtrabaho.)	4.00	FU	3.98	FU	3.99	FU
3. receive punishment for their poor job performance to let them push themselves to be better. (Ang mga empleyado ay tumatanggap ng parusa para sa kanilang mahinang pagganap sa trabaho upang itulak nila ang kanilang sarili na maging mas mahusay.)	4.00	FU	3.94	FU	3.97	FU
General Assessment	3.93	FU	3.93	FU	3.93	FU

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Fully Utilized (FU) 2.50-3.24 Utilized (U)
1.75-2.49 Moderately Utilized (MU) 1.00-1.74 Not Utilized (NU)

Extrinsic Motivators was Fully Utilized (3.93) as to the utilization level of motivating strategies of the human resource program of the GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing. The indicator “The employees seek to receive rewards for their job to keep them motivated to work” had the highest mean of **3.99** verbally interpreted as **Fully Utilized**. On the other hand, the indicator “The employees seek further knowledge and skills to go up the corporate ladder” had the lowest mean with **3.85** verbally interpreted as **Fully Utilized**.

This implies that, in addition in using intrinsic motivators as a motivating strategy, extrinsic motivators is also effective in crafting the human resource program of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation. Extrinsic motivator is a potent tool for shaping behavior and rewarding employees for their hard work, devotion, and excellent work. This type of motivator enables the employees to increase productivity, promote camaraderie in the workplace, maintain motivation, and improve job satisfaction.

Supporting this, Rosli et al. (2022) asserted that one kind of behavior modification known as operant conditioning was an extrinsic motivator. It made use of incentives and penalties to make certain actions more or less likely to occur again. Extrinsic motivators

helped support certain employees in maintaining their resolve and productivity in the face of obstacles at work, as it was generally most effective when motivating people to do difficult or uninteresting activities.

Research Question 5: Is there a significant relationship between the level of implementation of the human resource program and the level of performance of the employees of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation?

Table 5

Test of Significant Relationship between the Level of Implementation of Human Resource Program and the Level of Performance of the Employees of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation

Sales performance	Job Satisfaction of self-employed	r value	p value	Remarks	Decision
Ability	Productivity	.004	.970	Not Significant	Accept ho
	Output Quality	.190	.064	Not Significant	Accept ho
Motivation	Productivity	.173	.091	Not Significant	Accept ho
	Output Quality	.052	.616	Not Significant	Accept ho
Opportunity	Productivity	.040	.698	Not Significant	Accept ho
	Output Quality	.172	.094	Not Significant	Accept ho

There was no significant relationship between the level of implementation of the human resource program and the level of performance of the employees of the GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation. As shown in the probability values **0.970, 0.064, 0.091, 0.616, 0.698, and 0.094** which were greater than the level of significance at .05 and r values **0.004, 0.190, 0.173, 0.052, 0.040, and 0.172**. **Thus accept the null hypothesis.**

In conclusion, the level of implementation of the human resource program does not connect or associate with the level of performance of the employees of the GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation indicates that there are other factors that cam associate with the performance of the employees of GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation.

Another crucial component of employee performance is emotional intelligence. The ability to identify and control one's own emotions as well as those of others is referred to as emotional intelligence. People who work for companies are subject to human emotions. Sometimes workers become emotionally entangled in family matters, which prevents them from giving their jobs their whole attention. Moreover, employee performance may be positively or negatively impacted by work-life balance. The amount

of time and energy that an employee may commit to both their personal and professional lives is referred to as work-life balance. Given that the company provides sufficient support to the employees for optimum performance, factors such as emotional intelligence and work-life balance should also be considered in evaluating employee performance.

To support this claim, Dumaguing (2022) reiterated that scholars from throughout the world have conducted a great deal of research on employees' performance. They found that disengagement was correlated with both personal and professional traits. Employees were more likely to be contented with their jobs if they believed they had enough time for their personal life. As a result, they became more motivated, engaged, and dedicated to their work, which ultimately boosted their work output.

Research Question 6: Is there a significant relationship between the level of implementation of the human resource program and the utilization level of the motivating strategies of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation?

There was a significant relationship between the level of implementation of the human resource program and motivating strategies particularly the Implementation of Motivation and Extrinsic Motivating Strategies, significant relationship between Human Resource Program Opportunity and Motivating strategies such as Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivating Strategies. As shown in the probability values of **0.003**, **0.000**, and **0.005** which were less than the level of significance at 0.05 and with r values of **0.302**, **0.398**, and **0.284**. Thus, the hypothesis was rejected.

Table 6

Test of Significant Relationship between the Level of Implementation of Human Resource Program and Utilization Level of the Motivating Strategies of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation

Human resource program	Motivating Strategies	r value	p value	Remarks	Decision
Ability	Intrinsic	.147	.152	Not Significant	Accept ho
	Extrinsic	.187	.068	Not Significant	Accept ho
Motivation	Intrinsic	.111	.281	Not Significant	Accept ho
	Extrinsic	.302**	.003	Significant	Reject ho
Opportunity	Intrinsic	.398**	.000	Significant	Reject ho
	Extrinsic	.284**	.005	Significant	Reject ho

On the other hand, there was no significant relationship between the other variables of implementation of the human resource program and motivating strategies such as Ability and Motivating strategies, motivation, and intrinsic motivating strategies.

As shown in the probability values of **0.152**, **0.068**, and **0.281** which was more than the level of significance at 0.05 and with r values of **0.147**, **0.187**, and **0.111**. Thus, the hypothesis was accepted.

The human resource program of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation in terms of motivation is in line with the company's motivating strategies. Additionally, the motivating strategies are also in line with the company's human resource program in terms of opportunity. It is seen in the human resource program that the company motivates its employees, where the latter are motivated to work because their psychological needs for autonomy, relatedness, and competence are being met. Moreover, the employees are also motivated to work since they are getting external rewards from the company.

In human resource management, motivation is one of the most crucial strategies that companies invest in. The typical refrain in the majority of companies is that a certain individual lacks motivation, which has caused his or her performance to suffer. For this reason, businesses shell out enormous sums of money to plan training sessions and rewards that will inspire employees. Motivation can be defined as an individual's desire or drive to complete tasks and reach organizational goals.

Furthermore, when the setting fosters growth, employees will consistently give their best effort. One of the biggest motivators is the possibility of advancement. Employees worked with far greater zeal during periods when organizational doors were open and growth chances were plentiful than during periods when opportunities were rare or postponed for several reasons. Employees who are motivated to work show positive job performance, which in turn helps the company reach its objectives and goals.

To support this, Al-Tit (2020) suggested that using human resource programs to improve employee performance was seen as a combination of three things: skill development, incentive, and opportunity enhancement. Using the social exchange theory as support, analysts went on to say that when businesses implement HR initiatives, which workers were likely to view as a demonstration of the company's commitment to them, workers react in ways that advance corporate objectives. Employees viewed company activities such as programs aimed at improving skills, motivation, and opportunities as evidence of the company's support or dedication. In return, workers showed a positive attitude and enhanced output that contributed to the achievement of organizational goals.

Research Question 7: Based on the findings of the study, what enhanced program may be proposed?

Based on the findings of the study, several enhanced programs can be proposed to address the identified issues and improve the human resource program implementation and the employee performance of The Goldenhigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation.

Firstly, The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation can incorporate extra methods to enhance the company's human resource program in terms of ability,

motivation, and opportunity to maintain and improve productive employee performance. A comprehensive approach that would encompass the potential, drive, and aptitude of the staff members is creating a Human Capital Development Program. Employees would benefit from an entire human growth that would satisfy Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs, allow for a work-life balance, and advance their careers.

Secondly, it is noteworthy that the company offers its employees the same perks under the human resource program. But to have a better retention rate, the business needs to provide its workers with benefits that are based on talent and performance. The focus of the HR program ought to be on skill and performance. Benefits and awards ought to be given out following how well employees do their jobs overall. It should also take into account the employee's contribution to the company's accomplishment of its objectives.

Table 7
The Proposed Enhanced Plan

KEY AREAS	OBJECTIVES	STRATEGIES/ ACTIVITIES	TIME FRAME	PERSONS INVOLVED	SUCCESS INDICATRS
Implementation of human resource program in terms of Ability	Enhance ability aspect of the human resource program	Job-Skills matching of employees	Ongoing	Human Resource Department	Increased employee application rate
Implementation of human resource program in terms of Motivation	Enhance the motivation aspect of the human resource program	Offering performance based rewards	Ongoing	Human Resource Department	Increased scores in performance evaluation
Implementation of human resource program in terms of Opportunity	Enhance the opportunity aspect of the human resource program	Performance based promotion program	Ongoing	Human Resource Department	Increased employee retention rate
Motivating strategies in terms of Intrinsic Motivators	Enhance the intrinsic motivator aspect of the motivating strategies	Offering non-monetary benefits	Ongoing	Human Resource Department	Increased employee satisfaction feedback
Motivating strategies in terms of Extrinsic Motivators	Enhance the extrinsic motivator aspect of the motivating strategies	"Choose your own" rewards program	Ongoing	Human Resource Department	Increased employee satisfaction feedback
Employee performance in terms of Productivity	Improve employee productivity	Hire an Industrial Engineer to streamline workflow processes	3 Months	Heads, Operations Department	Increased production output and Decreased overtime
Employee performance in terms of Output Quality	Improve employee output quality	Quality assurance training and development	Ongoing	Heads, Quality Controllers	Decreased defect rate

Thirdly, the employees' responses indicate that they have to work overtime to complete the day's needed output. The employees' ability to combine their professional and personal lives will suffer as a result. As a result, the business needs to give a production output that can be achieved. An industrial engineer could be hired by the business to assist the management with capacity planning, layout planning, work design, and workflow management. As a result, the business would have a productive and successful operations system. Additionally, there would be no need for overtime because the staff could produce the necessary amount.

Furthermore, to maintain the company's successful incentive programs. Non-monetary rewards or perks must be part of the HR program. Cash awards are not the only way to recognize and thank employees. By providing non-cash awards, the organization can sustain the engagement, motivation, and excitement of its staff. Time for personal projects, flexibility in the workplace, extra time off, experiential rewards, and public recognition are a few examples. These would be very economical and increase worker engagement.

Apart from the aforementioned suggestion, the company might allow employees to select their awards. Giving workers the option to select their reward encouraged engagement and a driven workplace environment. Allowing workers to select their rewards improves the relationship between the organization and its workers and fosters a culture of trust and respect. It also makes workers feel appreciated. Thus, it may be possible to promote employee engagement and a positive work atmosphere.

Conclusions

After presenting the summary of the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. That The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation considers its employees to be valuable assets of any organization. Therefore, the company continuously improves its human resource management program. With this being said, the employees are really satisfied with the opportunity they have while working in the company. They have the opportunity to advance their skills and knowledge with the job that they do, which consequently helps with self-development and achievement of organizational goals. The statistics indicate that the employees of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation are relatively satisfied with the human resource program of the company in terms of ability because the company respects the competence of each employee. Moreover, employees have several reasons to be satisfied with the human resource program of the company in terms of motivation. Employees are motivated by doing performance evaluations regularly, following legal compensation-benefits programs, providing competitive compensation-benefits programs, focusing on the mental well-being of the employees, and giving rewards and punishment for job performance.

2. That the heads and employees both receive the same treatment from the management of The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation. Both the heads and employees benefit equally from the implementation of the human resource program of the company.

3. That the employees reach the hourly production output assigned to them and attain the required cycle time to finish an operation of the production process. Moreover, the employees exceed the required hourly production output assigned and they have a low absenteeism rate. These are important indicators and factors in the operations management of the company. Due to this positive performance of the employees, The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation reaches its operational goal of delivering the client's orders on time. In addition, the results also concluded that the performance of the employees in terms of Quality Output was rated Very High. The employees' final inspection output defect rate and in-line inspection defect rate are within company standards. Furthermore, the employees' Right First Time, which is a management strategy that estimates the percentage of usable products at the start of the production process, is within company standards. These indicators are vital for the company as they determine the reorder rate of the company's clients.

4. That extrinsic motivators are useful when creating the company's human resource program in addition to using internal motivators as a motivating method. An effective technique for modifying behavior and rewarding staff for their dedication, hard effort, and superior performance is the extrinsic motivator. With the help of this kind of motivator, workers can boost output, foster teamwork, stay motivated, and experience more job satisfaction. Some employees found that support from their external motivators helped them stay determined and productive even when faced with challenges at work.

5. That there are additional variables associated with The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation employees' performance. When assessing employee performance, aspects like emotional intelligence and work-life balance are also taken into account, provided that the organization offers enough support to its staff to enable them to perform at their best. The emotional intelligence of employees is another essential element of their performance. Emotional intelligence is the capacity to recognize and manage one's feelings as well as those of others. Employees of businesses are human beings with feelings. Workers occasionally become emotionally involved in family issues, which keeps them from focusing entirely on their work. Furthermore, work-life balance may have a favorable or unfavorable effect on employee performance. Work-life balance is the quantity of time and effort that an employee can devote to both their personal and professional lives.

6. That the motivating strategies are being applied in the opportunity aspect of the human resource program of The Goldenhigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation. When the work environment is supportive of growth, employees consistently give their best work. The opportunity aspect is seen as an effective motivating strategy used in the human resource program of the company. Employees work with far greater vigor during periods when organizational doors are open and growth opportunities are available.

7. That the proposed Enhanced Program is of great importance in addressing the identified findings in the human resource program of The Goldenhigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation. The Enhanced Program serves as a complete framework for implementing directed interventions and driving improvement. Eventually, the Enhanced Program guides improvement efforts, enhancing the human resource program, motivating strategies, and employee performance.

Recommendations

The following recommendations have been formulated based on the summarized findings and derived conclusions:

1. To sustain and enhance productive employee performance, The GoldenHigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation may implement additional strategies for the company's human resource program in terms of ability, motivation, and opportunity. One overall strategy that would encapsulate the ability, motivation, and opportunity of the employees is establishing a Human Capital Development Program. This would give the employees overall human development in terms of work-life balance, career development, and meeting Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs.

2. The company may offer skill-performance-based benefits to its employees. The human resource program must be skill-performance-centric. It may give rewards and benefits based on the overall job performance of the employees. Moreover, it may consider the contribution of the employee to the company's achievement of organizational goals.

3. The company may provide an achievable required production output. The former must take into consideration the output capacity of the employees. Moreover, the company should evaluate the production line performance. The manufacturing company's production line is its fundamental component. By carefully examining each manufacturing facility and its daily capacity, the management can map how the production lines are performing. Hence, an efficient and achievable production output can be given to the employees.

4. The company may hire an industrial engineer who would help the management with its capacity planning, layout planning, work design, and workflow management. Hence, the company would have an effective and efficient operations system. Moreover, the employees would be able to meet their required output without needing overtime.

5. The human resource program may include non-monetary incentives or benefits. Employee rewards don't have to be in the form of cash. The company may maintain its employees' enthusiasm, motivation, and engagement by offering non-monetary rewards. Examples are 1) time to work on their projects, 2) flexible working, 3) additional time off, 4) experiential rewards, and 5) public recognition. These would provide great value for money and help engage employees more.

6. The company may let their employees choose their rewards. Offering employees the chance to choose their reward helps create a sense of engagement that promotes a motivated company culture. Giving employees the freedom to choose their rewards strengthens the bond between the company and employees and creates a climate of mutual respect and trust. It also helps employees feel valued. Thus, a positive work environment and employee motivation may be fostered.

7. The company may utilize the proposed Enhanced Program. This comprehensive plan includes strategies for effective human resource program implementation, motivating strategies utilization, and promoting a culture of continuous improvement. By prioritizing these initiatives, the employees of The Goldenhigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation can increase their job performance. Moreover, management support and sufficient financial resources are vital to effectively implement the enhanced program. Furthermore, regular evaluation of the enhanced program may be done to assess its effectiveness. By following the proposed enhanced program, the company can strive towards its goals of improvement and increased employee performance.

8. To deepen understanding and contribute to the field of human resource management in the garment manufacturing industry, the results of this study can be expanded upon in several ways for further research. Three (3) fields can be recommended, 1) conducting employee-centered research, 2) doing a qualitative approach in future research with the purpose of better understanding the employees' experiences, and 3) evaluating the effectiveness of the proposed enhanced program of the study. The Goldenhigh-Garments Manufacturing Corporation will have a great opportunity to do all necessary analysis about the implementation of the human resource program, utilization of motivating strategies, and employee performance as a result of this initiative.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Some ethical concerns were addressed since this study needed respondents, specifically employees of a company, to participate. To protect the participants' privacy and safety, it was essential to take these ethical considerations into account. Consent and confidentiality are two important ethical considerations that were taken into account throughout the research process. The researcher communicated all significant information about the study, including its goal and objective, to obtain the consensus of the chosen participants. The importance of the respondent's role in the completion of the research was made clear to them by elaborating on these crucial facts. The respondents were also notified that they could pull out their involvement in the study at any time. As a result, participants were not compelled to take part in the study. The participants' privacy was further protected by the researcher by not using their names or other identifying information. Only information that was pertinent to resolving the research questions was provided.

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